

ZAMBIAN DETERGENT PASTE BRANDING STRATEGY IN AFRICA**Singuwa Chimuka***PhD, Assistant Lecturer and a scholar in International Relations affiliated with the Department of Theory and History of International Relations at the Peoples' Friendship University of Russia (RUDN University)**ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0812-9234>***Daniel Kumafan Terzungwe***second-year Master's student in International Relations at the Department of Theory and History of International Relations,**Peoples' Friendship University of Russia***Singuwa Gospel***fourth-year Political Science student in the Department of Comparative Political Science at Peoples' Friendship University of Russia (RUDN University)***Abstract**

The detergent industry is critical to maintaining cleanliness and hygiene in both domestic and industrial settings. The need for detergents in Zambia and Africa is constantly increasing due to population increase, urbanization, and higher living standards. For businesses and investors in the region, the detergent manufacture and supply sector represents a significant prospect. The goal of this paper is to critically examine Trade Kings' branding strategy in relation to the boom brand and determine how the company has managed to place its brand in the eyes of its customers. In the introduction, the terms brand, branding, and brand strategy will be established as a starting point. Following that, Trade Kings Company will be introduced. The subject will be concluded with a review of Trade Kings' brand strategy for positioning the boom product in the eyes of consumers.

Keywords: Trade kings, Boom, Detergent, Branding, Zambia.

Introduction

To comprehend Trade Kings' brand strategy, one must first comprehend the concept of branding. A brand is a name, term, design, symbol, or any other attribute that distinguishes one seller's good or service from another. Brands are used in business, marketing, and advertising to increase brand recognition and equity for the recognized object, benefiting the brand's customers, owners, and shareholders. Branding is all about convincing people that the company is offering the greatest product or service for the consumers from the moment they come into contact with one of the company's products, services, or marketing materials (Tony Hardy, 2020). According to Copper (2003), a brand is "a name, term, sign, symbol, or design, or a combination of them, intended to identify and distinguish the goods or services of one seller or group of sellers from those of competitors." The amalgamation of a company or product's reputation, image, and level of familiarity is known as consumer branding. When something or someone has a successful branding campaign, it becomes a household name, the first thing that comes to mind when your target audience has a need or desire related to your brand.

Anyim, Mba, and Ekwoaba (2012) define a brand strategy as an organization's or company's strategic plan to grow, develop, and promote its product brand. It also includes messages the company sends out to its customers and potential customers periodically to foster customer relationships. This description aligns with that provided by Greer (1995), who described a brand strategy as a long-term plan with the goal of creating a successful brand. Businesses, according to him, employ the plan to build a specific image. Trade Kings, for ex-

ample, has a successful brand strategy. Customers associate with the company more when they use the brand, which influences purchasing decisions. An effective brand strategy should be well-planned and implemented across all business areas in order to increase financial performance, competitive advantage, and customer experience (Hunger & Wheelen 2006).

About trade kings

Trade kings' group is one of the largest privately owned manufacturers in southern Africa. It is a wholly Zambian owned business, the largest Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) manufacturer in Zambia and amongst the largest in sub-saharan africa featuring world class manufacturing facilities in Zambia and Zimbabwe, trade kings have proudly been manufacturing and exporting the highest quality Zambian made products within Zambia, southern Africa and beyond.

Since 1995, now celebrating 25 years of high quality, trusted and affordable products, our portfolio has grown dramatically, and the group has diversified extensively. Today, Trade Kings is a globally competitive group of businesses driven by global standards, manufacturing practices and an aggressive research and development agenda which has led to the high levels of innovation, constant improvement and a host of highly specialized, technically advanced products in recent years.

In 2019, the export of detergent paste from Zambia amounted to an approximate value of 55 million U.S. dollars. This was an increase in value in comparison to the preceding year, when roughly 53 million U.S. dollars of the products were exported. Furthermore, the Democratic Republic of the Congo was one of the main trade partners of Zambia in terms of soap and washing preparation exports with a share of just over 86 percent.

Export value of detergent paste from Zambia from 2015 to 2019 (in million U.S. dollars)

Source: [Statista 2023](#)

The scope of Trade Kings Group today includes four distinct clusters namely, food, beverage, laundry, home and personal care products and steel. The product range manufactured under each category is listed below:

- **Food:** Confectionery, biscuits, baking powder, custard powder, castor sugar, soya fillets, spice mixes, breakfast cereals, infant cereals, potato crisps and maize snacks.
- **Beverage:** Maheu, Chibwantu, milkshakes, instant coffee and tea beverages, carbonated soft drinks, energy drinks, juices, milk and dairy juice blends.
- **Laundry, Home and Personal Care Products:** Detergent (powder and paste), bleaches, floor cleaners, toilet cleaners, dishwashing liquids, all-purpose creams, scouring powders, window and glass cleaners, bath soaps, hygiene soaps, beauty soaps, hair soaps, glycerine, hand sanitisers, liquid handwashing soaps, antiseptic liquids and fabric conditioners.
- **Steel:** Steel re-bar, angles and channels.

The drive for diversification and a belief in the establishment of specialised businesses, to ensure focus and innovation within each category, has led to the Trade Kings Group we know today. Trade Kings Group is comprised of Trade Kings, Big Tree Beverages, Big Tree Brands (featuring several specialist sub businesses focusing independently on infant nutrition, cereals and baking products and spices), Dairy Gold, Swiss Bake, Yoyo Foods and Universal Mining and Chemicals Limited (UMCIL).

Since the companies first product, Blue Boom Detergent Paste and the establishment of the now iconic BOOM brand, Trade Kings has developed a portfolio of many of the foremost brands in the Zambian and southern African markets across the categories and sectors in which we operate. Thanks to the support of the Zambian people and those in all ten of the southern African countries in which we operate, Trade Kings and its brands have become household names and are synonymous with quality, reliability and value for money across the portfolio and the group of companies.

At Trade Kings, we aim to create a connection between its products and their impact on people's lives.

From the promotion of affordable hygiene with Yebo Carbolic soaps, the health benefits of MediHerb Ayurvedic herbal soaps and the antibacterial family protection of Hygienix hygiene soap, to the livelihoods that selling the confectionary lines like Amazon and Milkit creates. Trade king's role in the lives of others is never taken for granted and inspires the companies' business approach, culture and way of thinking.

Trade Kings purpose is "Improving Lives", whether through our emphasis on providing branded products of superior quality and value, value addition and shared value projects with local suppliers, growers or producers, our corporate social responsibility initiatives and public private partnerships through the Trade Kings Foundation or our focus on women's and youth empowerment initiatives. All the companies' efforts are aligned to deliver this single minded promise. Both evident in the history and the actions of the founders we aim to improve the lives of its consumers nationally, regionally and internationally both now and for future generations through carefully selected strategic projects.

Trade Kings Boom detergent paste branding strategy.

Trade Kings started off as a manufacturer of boom detergent paste in 1995 and has since expanded and enhanced their product line over the course of 29 years. They currently produce more than 300 distinct items. Other nations including Malawi, Botswana, Namibia, South Africa, and Zimbabwe are part of their market. Through the success of its main brand, the company established a trend for reasonably priced, high-quality locally produced goods. Attitude factors, such as brand quality perception, are the main determinants of detergent brand choice in the Zambian market. Perceptions of value for money are closely behind these.

According to Cheelo and Munalula (2005), the mother of Trade Kings is boom. They are not going to put it aside for any reason. Indeed, the company has expanded its boom brand. Many more goods with the brand name boom include scouring powder, dishwashing liquid, antibacterial, and bleaching agent. While they appear to be selling new detergent pastes, they are

indirectly advertising boom detergent paste and boom bubble plus washing powder. They have built brand loyalty for boom in recent years to the point where people believe that everything bearing the brand name 'boom' is of high quality and provides good value for money.

Several brand strategies have been implemented by Trade Kings Ltd. to market the company's products. These positioning techniques include the cost-driven, product quality-based, and price-based approaches. The quickest way for the company to keep gaining market share from rivals and protecting its brands from new entrants is through the price-based strategy. It depends on how valuable consumers think a brand is. Comparing the costs of other imported goods at chain stores and supermarkets across the nation, such as Shoprite, makes this clear at the moment. Prices for boom products such as washing powder and toilet cleaners are relatively cheaper compared to other products like Dettol, sun-light powder and Omo. This pricing strategy has been effectively used when launching products in markets where demand tends to change remarkably as prices change.

According to Graham and Brigitte (2008), price positioning refers to the process of assigning a price to a good or service that falls within a specific range. The pricing placement of a product signifies its standing vis-à-vis its rivals within a particular market and among distinct client segments. This positioning approach aids in determining the amount of quality that can be offered at a price that is less expensive than that of the competitors. It is intended for customers who require a less expensive option from which they may still obtain the highest level of satisfaction. Usually, the only way you can actually accomplish this is if you have access to techniques and technologies that your rivals still cannot afford. It is crucial to minimize the negative effects of this method on the quality of your product, even when using it.

Secondly, in order to ensure recurring purchases, the Company has implemented a quality-based position brand strategy. According to Greer (1995), product quality-based positioning is related to other brand strategies such as value or price-based positioning and is typically used in conjunction with one or more other strategies for greater impact. Good quality is enough to distinguish a brand and leave an impact on the consumer's mind. This method is used to verify that the product quality is accurately represented and that the quality promised is delivered (Blackston, 2016).

The third element is value positioning (Graham & Brigitte, 2008). This positioning technique can be used to leverage the perceived value and quality of the goods and services being delivered. With value positioning, your business should be depicted as a source of high-end or luxury items and services that are not necessarily available to the general public. Clients should see a clear representation of exclusivity. It is also clear that

Trade Kings' boom brand has been exploited as a family brand, echoing the value for the African family in its marketing advertisements. Due to its affordable pricing, the boom brand is utilized by people of all social classes and has been used by children, grandparents, and parents to demonstrate how customers use it from childhood to adulthood in the African context. To further emphasize the importance of the brand, the company has included "improving lives" as one of its marketing slogans.

Trade Kings has made a major regional impact in the manufacturing sector, and emerging economies are driving enormous demand from society as a whole (Chipeta, 2017). The company's main goal is to supply branded goods of the highest caliber and worth to customers both domestically and abroad, both today and in the future. One of the newest products on the market, Boom toilet cleaner is a Trade Kings Limited brand that was just introduced in the nation. For the individual user, the Boom toilet cleaner is more compact and portable. Additionally, Boom toilet cleanser was created especially with a pleasant scent. In addition to these two product features, it is less expensive than comparable goods like Dettol and Harpic. Competitors currently produce similar goods outside of the nation (Cheelo & Munalula, 2019). The majority of these rivals are located outside of Zambia. The majority of them are found in South Africa and other places. Boom toilet cleaning will have an advantage over other goods since it will be more accessible to Zambian consumers.

Furthermore, there are advantages to marketing boom as a family brand. It significantly minimizes the price of product introduction and ongoing promotional investment. The company must promote only one brand, which, if successful, may sell the complete product line. It also becomes easy to align the distribution channel members. In marketing, a family brand name has been discovered to be particularly cost effective. In addition, if one product does extraordinarily well, it is entirely feasible that favorable spillover effects will occur for other products promoted under the same brand (McCracken, 2018). A major flaw with this method is that it fails to grasp that any product can be given a unique identity by a good brand, which can help it succeed.

Consumer Market Segmentation

The global soap detergent market was valued at USD 100.53 billion in 2022 and is predicted to grow to USD 149.4 billion by 2032, with a 4.5% revenue CAGR during the forecast period. Rising consumer demand for personal care products, increased cleanliness and hygiene awareness, and rising urbanization in developing countries are all important factors driving market revenue development. Because of the growing demand for environmentally friendly and sustainable cleaning products, manufacturers are working on developing technologically advanced and green energy-based soap detergents (Plehve & Morozkin, 2019).

Soap Detergent Market Size, 2022-2032

Geographical, demographic, psychological, and behavioural segments make up the boom product market (McCarthy, 200). The boom brand, which is distributed at retail establishments in Zambia, is primarily focused on the Zambian market through geographic segmentation. In warm, temperate climates, consumers require body products and soap for personal hygiene. A dense market potential exists in Zambia due to the country's high number of residents, visitors, and other people who use hygiene goods. This is in addition to the country's extreme heat.

In terms of demographics, most people need washing and cleaning products, and older generations of users are aware of boom soap's history in the market as well as its presence as a well-known brand (Hoskisson & Hitt, 2006). Young customers also respect hygiene and the environment; therefore, they seek out more natural items to help them be "green." "Boom items are affordable to consumers of all income levels and educational levels since they are a necessity.

Boom items appeal to various lifestyles, including families, backpackers, adventurers, and young adults, among others, according to psychological segmentation (Rothbard, 2004). Individuals with a preference for more natural products and Zambian-owned goods constitute a significant customer niche. The brand boom gives high-quality items to consumers, and the brand itself appeals to a wide range of consumers. Furthermore, in partnership with Flash Transporting Company, the Company uses painted buses in Trade Kings colours to exhibit its products (Ayanwale, Aimi, & Ayanbimipe, 2005).

In terms of behavioural segmentation, the benefits of purchasing boom goods include their various uses, low cost, natural ingredients, and effective hygiene use, all of which meet consumers' expectations as well as their needs. Furthermore, the 'boom' brand is well-known in the industry, and buyers have remained loyal to the brand over the years due to its dependability.

There is a medium volume usage because soap is purchased as a need, but it competes with shower gels and other goods.

Conclusion

Trade Kings is a significant consumer goods company in Africa, with a diversified product line. To build a significant market presence, the company has employed many branding tactics. It was the only Zambian brand in the Top 10 Most Admired Brands list. For the second year in a row, Trade Kings has appeared in the Top 10 Most Admired Brands, having acquired 10 ranking points, firmly placing the Zambian conglomerate in the Top 10 Most Admired African Brands and second only to Dangote in the fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) category. The important criteria considered include innovation in light of Trade Kings' massive investments in contemporary machinery and technology, product quality, and managerial quality.

For a company like Trade Kings which is 29 years old, it is no mean achievement to find themselves among the top 50 most admired brands in Africa competing with the likes of international megabrands that include Nike, Apple and Samsung while ranking in the top 10 with African giants like Dangote, MTN, Anbessa Shoes, Econet, Safaricom, Shoprite, Glo and Tusker.

From humble beginnings, the company has grown into a colossus that has spread across the southern African region. With a vast product range extending from confectionary and detergents to beverages and dairy products, Trade Kings Group is not content in its growth and looks to continue "Improving Lives" through innovative products that are of the highest quality, affordable and available to the vast majority of low-income households in Zambia and across Africa.

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